

ADVANTAGES OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Annotation. In this article, the impact of digital technologies on various aspects of life, in particular, what digital technologies should be used in the field of sports, are put forward. In addition, the importance of physical education for students' lives and the possibility of using various technological methods to achieve the goal in the course of the lesson are shown.

Key words: physical education, digital trend, sports equipment, sports training, style, technical change.

To date, digital technologies are rapidly entering the socio-economic life of each country, and the use of digital tools is also important for the development of economic development of Uzbekistan in the context of the globalization of the world economy and the development of technologies. In Particular, President Sh.M.As Mirziyov noted, " Of course, we know very well that the formation of a digital economy requests the necessary infrastructure, a lot of funds and labor resources. However, no matter how difficult it is, when do we get into this business if we don't start today?! Tomorrow will be too late. Therefore, the active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities for the next 5 years”.

In our society, it is possible to further develop the trend of digital education through modern information technologies and create qualitatively new models of production, change the format of Education, Health, Public Administration, communication between people, and define a new paradigm of development of society as a whole. At the current level of development of society, the process of using digital technologies implants, first of all, the digital transformation of the main functions in the activity, namely, transition to new digital operating and business models in production and management. Similarly, the digital transformation in education should be understood as a complete reconstruction of the educational process, which includes not only teaching methods and tools, but also changes in the competence model, changes in the semantic model of the educational program, approaches to assessing teacher activity. Also, digital management of regular

processes in an educational institution: personnel controls, management of educational downloads, financial management, document management, that is, all activities of the units of an educational organization: educational, methodological, scientific research, etc.

In the context of digital transformation, the main tasks of higher education in general education and physical education are the task of “teaching how to learn”, preparing for the rapid changes taking place in the information society, forming effective interaction with them. In a certain sense, it should be said that employees determine promising areas of training future specialists, changes in the structure of knowledge and skills, which require the transition from a cognitive school to a school of skills, skills, qualifications, which is necessary to solve professional problems in socio - economic conditions that are constantly changing. The need of modern society for qualified specialists in the conditions of such professional activity creates new requirements for their training.

Using technical devices based on empirical data, the dialectical search for new, more advanced tools and methods and the optimization of training conditions now took place. In the design of devices and simulators, new knowledge in ergonomics, biomechanics, engineering psychology and design is used.

To improve their performance in everyday life, leisure activities and work, people have long created and used various technical means. In the process of human evolution and technical changes, these tools were constantly complicated and improved. The same happened with the creation of sports equipment and exercise equipment. The world of sports is in constant change socially, economically and spiritually, however, if someone suggests the most common changes in sports in the last century, it will be the use of technology. Modern science now allows athletes to move up, move faster and, most importantly, be safer. Technological innovation is not only the equipment and sportswear used by athletics, but also bicycles, tennis rackets and swimsuits are comfortable and meet the requirements of the present. In the course of the research carried out, the use of digital technology has shown its significant place in achieving high results in competitions between athletes and their opponents. Digital technology has not only affected sports results. During the study, it is of great importance that studies involving certain forms of ICT such as wikis, web, etc.stimulate readers and contribute to knowledge acquisition. Nevertheless, there is a check on the use of videotape technology to develop learning in physical education. Using it will have enormous potential and opportunities.The following methods were used for research in the field of physical education and sports: the analysis of scientific and methodological literature, the methods of creating and using digital information technologies in the field of physical education and sports were studied.

Sports training creates realistic conditions for students to develop comprehensively, self-awareness and self-affirmation through their chosen Sports. Modern aspects of educational process management in higher education institutions have not yet been developed scientifically enough. At the same time, the commercialization of sports training in higher educational institutions negatively affects the level of sports training of students.

One of the indispensable conditions for the successful competitive activities of qualified basketball players is the use of modern offensive systems that help to maximize the abilities of athletes. Most experts in this sport recognize the high importance of an effective emergency attack with a quick break. Professionals in the field of physical education and sports “...the channels of transition between mass sports and elite sports also emphasize the importance of” to what extent, first of all, the system of training the reserves of the national team of the country is established."The physical education of students is a system that is constantly being improved based on the accumulation of new experimental research data, advanced experience and scientific and technological progress.

International perspectives of new technologies in physical education many scientists and practitioners present their perspectives on the science and practice of digital innovation in physical education. They highlight scientific work on digital technology, asking what evidence exists for teachers, as well as what narratives and examples can help physical education teachers and coaches if they want to introduce technology into their daily practice.

In general physical education and Sports, digital technology education can be used for the following purposes:

- dynamic indicators of the reaction of functional systems to load (transferable gadgets and special programs);
- improving the psycho-emotional state of students (smart floor technologies and "smart wall");
- Organization of motor activity competitions using technology touch controller (Just Dance [2] similar to a computer game, etc.);
- allows the formation of a modern digital educational environment

The introduction of a continuous physical education model in Uzbekistan, which has a positive effect on the educational emigration of the best students due to which the network helps to teach and prevent the most out of each other talented youth allows the creation and placement of didactic materials on resources in other regions.

In place of the conclusion, it should be said that the role of any forms and styles of physical education and sports in the growth and development of students is incomparable. the organization of practical work, taking into account their age and pedagogical characteristics in increasing the physical development and training of

students, further increases the effectiveness of this process. The use of technical means in increasing the general physical fitness of students is a requirement of the present day. Because the process of modern sports education cannot be tasted without technical means. Such a technological approach to physical education lessons in the process of modern physical education, firstly, increases the interest of students in physical education, secondly, allows them to have a special impact on various organs and systems, and thirdly, increases the effectiveness of the physical education process.

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